

Clinical Profile and Radiological Correlation of Recurrent Stroke

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Abstract

Background: Recurrent stroke is a new cerebrovascular event which occurs after the stabilization of the previous stroke. There is a wide range of clinical presentations and no significant difference between the first and recurrent strokes regarding the type of stroke. After stroke, survivors tend to focus on rehabilitation and recovery but preventing another stroke is a key concern. Systemic evaluation of recurrent stroke cases can help to identify risk factors, etiologies to choose the appropriate treatment and to reduce the risk of recurrence. **Methods and materials:** It was a descriptive cross-sectional study carried out at medicine and neuromedicine department of Dhaka Medical College and Hospital for 6 months, where a total of 100 patients were enrolled. Data was collected in questionnaire by interview who gave consent and fulfilled inclusion criteria. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software. **Result:** Our study revealed that out of 100 patients, 72% were male and 28% were female, mean age 57.45 years, most were from 60-69 age group (44%). About 32% had completed higher secondary education and 46% belongs to lower middle class family. Most of the event occurred during daytime (44%) and about 47% respondents were sedentary workers. In present study, 78% respondents suffered from ischaemic stroke and rest of them (22%) had haemorrhagic stroke. About 66 (66%) of them presented with hypertension, 42(42%) with diabetes mellitus, 46(46%) had dyslipidaemia and 35(35%) presented with heart diseases. Among the patient with heart diseases, majority had IHD (63%, 22), followed by arrhythmia (57%, 20), valvular heart disease (54%, 19) and congestive heart failure (CHF) (17%, 6). Most of them (62%) were smoker, 22% chewed betel nuts, 12% chewed tobacco and 8% were alcoholic. Majority of the respondents presented with weakness of half of the body (68%) and GCS was more than 10 in 52 ischaemic stroke cases and 8 haemorrhagic stroke cases. In ischaemic stroke, middle cerebral artery (MCA) was involved in 71% cases, followed by posterior cerebral artery (PCA) (16%), anterior cerebral artery (8%), basilar artery (5%) and in haemorrhagic stroke, affected regions were basal ganglia, internal capsule and thalamus (55%, 12), followed by temporo-parietal region (36%, 8) and posterior fossa (9%, 2). **Conclusion:** Present study finds out stroke type, risk factors, etiologies and radiological findings of recurrent stroke. A better understanding of the risk factors, etiologies could lead a better secondary prevention and thus will limit the future stroke burden in society.

Introduction

Stroke is the clinical syndrome caused by neurological signs and symptoms that develop due to rapid onset of

focal cerebral dysfunction with a vascular cause and that last more than 24 hours [48]. Recurrent stroke is defined as a new cerebrovascular event which occurs

More Information

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Keywords:

Recurrent stroke, focal cerebral dysfunction, gender correlation, risk factors.

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after the stabilization of the previous stroke [1]. Stroke comprises disorder of vascular system that causes in ischemia, infraction and haemorrhage in the brain.

Risk of stroke recurrence varies depending upon the types of cerebrovascular diseases and risk factors [48]. The risk of recurrence is highest for all types of cerebrovascular diseases in the first year after the stroke and it decreases gradually over time [2,3].

According to National Stroke Association of USA, approximately 795000 Americans experience a stroke each year, about 185000 of those strokes are recurrent strokes [49]. At least one in four (25% -35%) of 795000 Americans who have a stroke each year will have another stroke within their lifetime [48]. Within five years of a stroke, 24% of women and 42% of men will experience a recurrent stroke [50].

There is a wide range of clinical presentation of stroke or recurrent stroke. The predominant symptom is hemiplegia [4], other common neurological symptoms are dysphasia, dysarthria, dysphagia, visual disturbance, brain stem deficit and loss of consciousness etc. The consequences of a stroke, the type of function affected and severity depend on where in the brain it has occurred and the extent of damage [51].

There is no significant difference between the first and recurrent strokes regarding type of stroke [48]. When the previous strokes in recurrent strokes were evaluated, the previous strokes were ischemic in 80.9% of the ischemic strokes and haemorrhagic types in 43.4% of the haemorrhagic strokes [5].

Cerebrovascular diseases are a leading cause of death and disability and cause individual and socio-economic losses [48]. Recurrent strokes increase the disability-mortality rates [1,6].

Systemic evaluation of recurrent stroke cases can help to identify risk factors, to choose the appropriate treatments and to reduce the risk of recurrence [48]. In multivariate analysis, recurrence was more frequently associated with a history of TIA, atrial fibrillation, male gender, hypertension, daily alcohol consumption, smoking, diabetes, ischemic heart disease, serum cholesterol or haematocrit [52]. Mortality was almost doubled compared with patients with a first ever stroke. In survivors, however, both neurologic and functional outcomes and the speed of recovery were, in general, similar in the two groups [7,52].

HTN was the most frequently encountered and statistically significantly higher risk factor in the first and recurrent strokes [48]. This finding is consistent with the literature [2,8-10]. The other risk factors were hyperlipidemia, DM, cigarette smoking and AF, respectively. AF increased statistically significantly with age [13,48].

The relation between risk factors and the recurrence of stroke shows considerable variation [48]. According to

Copenhagen study, recurrence is related to TIA, AF, male gender and HTN (7). Barchay's compiler article emphasizes that recurrence rate of stroke can be reduced by 30-40%. The same article states that while hyperlipidemia is an important risk factor for the first stroke, its effect is not clear on the recurrent stroke [12]. DM is correlated particularly with recurrent stroke [5,48].

Wu T found that stroke recurrence was correlated with HTN, AF and cigarette smoking in the Chinese population and that getting controlling this risk factors decreased the recurrence rate considerably [13]. The higher recurrence rates in Chinese compared to western populations were attributed by the authors to modifiable risk factors which were not being managed [2,3,9,10,12,14,15].

When the first and recurrent ischemic strokes were evaluated with regard to stroke etiologies, unidentified cause of strokes, cardioembolic strokes and stroke due to large vessel diseases were seen to be the leading causes in both groups, respectively [5,48].

Knowledge of risk factors and etiologic group can help to predict recurrence of stroke and prevent death. Effective treatment of modifiable risk factors identified in recurrent stroke groups and prioritizing the investigation of cardioembolic risk factors in elderly are significant in terms of primary and secondary stroke prevention [48].

Materials and Methods

It was a cross-sectional observational study conducted in Department of Medicine and Department of Cardiology, Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH) in between July 2016 to June 2017. All patients who were admitted in Department of Medicine, and Cardiology with hypertension (systolic BP 140 or >140mm Hg and diastolic BP 90 or >90 mm Hg) with retinopathy and other target organ damage were enrolled in the study. Total 384 patients were included of both sexes. Participants were properly informed about the nature of the study and consent obtained from those willing to participate. Detailed history including duration of hypertension, medications received, degree of control of hypertension and any history suggestive of adverse cardiac events along with prescribed medication were obtained. Thorough examination was done to evaluate presence of hypertension, evidence of hypertensive retinopathy, left ventricular hypertrophy and nephropathy. Blood pressure was recorded in sitting position in a bed by Auscultatory method with Sphygmomanometer (ALPK2, Japan) and stethoscope (Littman, Japan) in two settings at 15 min interval and classify according to NICE, 2011 guideline.

Degree of hypertensive retinopathy was assessed by direct ophthalmoscopic (HEINE, German) examination will be defined by Gunn and Keith, Barker and Wagener classification. Ophthalmoscope were done in a dark

room, patient was sitted in a chair after 1% tropicamide eye drops given in each eye. After full dilation of pupil, right eye was examined by right eye and left eye was examined by left eye [53]. During ophthalmoscope; optic media, optic disc, retinal blood vessels and retinal background were observed. Retinal findings were cross examined by an ophthalmologist in the department of Ophthalmology in DMCH.

M-mode, two dimensional echocardiography was performed for all study patients in the department of Cardiology in DMCH, in left partial decubitus position, using a HITACHI ALOKA ECHO machine (Model-F37,Hitachi Aloka MedicalLt, China.) and a 2.5-3.5 MHz electrical transducer. End diastolic internal diameter (LVIDd), septal wall thickness (SWT) and posterior wall thickness (PWT) were calculated from the two dimensionally guided M-mode tracing and measured in five consecutive cardiac cycle. LVH was defined as, when SWT is >11 mm and/or PWT is >11 mm in during diastole. Before echocardiography, ECG was done for each patient and find out ST segment and T-wave changes [53].

Spot urine sample was collected and perform ACR for proteinuria. Investigation were done to ascertain presence of microalbuminuria by spot urine sample examination for ACR (urinary albumin-creatinine ratio) in the department of Biochemistry in Banghabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) by Dimension Clinical Chemistry System (Particle-enhanced Turbidimetic Inhibition Immunoassay Method). Subjects were classified according to the ACR: <30 mg/g as normoalbuminuric, 30-300 mg/g as microalbuminuric and >300 mg/g as macroalbuminuric or overt proteinuria.Data were presented in tabulated form and were analyzed using computer based program Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for Windows version 23.

Observation and Results

Figure 1: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Sex (n=100)

The pie chart shows that among the respondents Most of them (72%, 72) were male and rest of them were female (28%, 28).

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents According to Age (n=100)

Minimum	30
Maximum	72
SD	3.56
Range	42
Mean	57.45

The table shows that among the respondents minimum age was found 30 years, maximum 72 years, mean age was found 57.45 years with SD 3.56 years.

Table 2: Age Group Distribution of the Respondents (n=100)

Age	Number
30-39	5
40-49	16
50-59	31
60-69	44
>70	4
Total	100

The table shows that most of the respondents (44%) were from 60-69 age group.

Figure 2: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Marital Status (n=100)

The pie chart shows that among the respondents most of them (98%) were married and the rest were (02%) unmarried.

Figure 3: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Occupation (n=100)

The pie chart shows among the respondent's majority of them (34%, 34) were retired, followed by businessman (22%,22), housewives (17%, 17), 8 of them were private service, 6 were govt. employee and 13 were from other occupation.

Figure 5: Distribution of the Respondents According to Education (n=100)

The bar chart shows that among the respondent's majority completed higher secondary education (32%,32) followed by primary (27%, 27), secondary (20%, 20), graduation complete (13%, 13) and illiterate (8%, 8).

Figure 4: Distribution of the Respondents According to Socioeconomic Status (n=100)

The pie chart shows among the respondent's majority of them were from lower middle class (46%, 46), followed by upper middle class (32%, 32), lower class (12%, 12) and upper class (10%, 10).

Figure 6: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Nature of Work (n=100)

The pie chart shows among the respondent's majority of them were (47%) sedentary workers, followed by moderate (39%) workers and severe workers (14%).

Figure 7: Distribution of the Respondents According to Type of Stroke (n=100)

The pie chart shows among the respondent’s majority of them (78%, 78) had infarction and rest of them (22%,22) had haemorrhage.

Figure 8: Distribution of the respondents according to their time of onset of the event (n=100)

The pie chart shows among the respondents majority of them (44%) had the event at day time, followed by early morning (27%), after a stressful event(18%) and rest of them (11%) had their stroke at their sleep.

Figure 9: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Symptoms at Onset (Multiple Answer)

The bar chart shows among the respondent’s majority of them presented with weakness of half of the body (68%),history of sudden fall (55%), unable to talk (33%), vertigo (16%), headache (09%), vomiting (26%), convulsion (14%),visual disturbance (08%),sphincter disturbance(38%), alteration of behavior(8%) and other symptoms (29).

Figure 10: Distribution of the Respondents According to their History of Past Illness (Multiple Response)

The bar chart shows among the respondents 66 of them presented with hypertension, 43 with diabetes

mellitus, 46 had dyslipidaemia, 35 presented with heart disease and 4 of them had collagen disease.

Figure 11: Distribution of the Respondents According to Type of Stroke and Their History of Past Illness (Multiple Response)

The bar chart shows in all four groups of respondent's infarction was more common than heamorrhage. But among the respondents those with hypertension or heart disease they are more likely to suffer from infarctive stroke than heamorrhage.

Figure 12: Distribution of the Respondents with History of Heart Disease According to Their Disease Specification of the Diagnosis (n=35)

The pie chart shows among the respondents those who had a history of heart disease (35), majority had IHD (63%, 22), followed by arrhythmia (57%, 20), Valvular heart disease (54%, 19) and Congestive heart failure (CHF) (17%, 6).

Figure 13: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Personal History

The bar chart shows among the respondents 62 of them presented with the history of smoking, 8 with alcohol consumption, 22 chewed bettle nuts and 12 of them had history of tobacco chewing.

Figure 14: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Drug History (n=100)

The bar chart shows among the respondents, 42 hypertensive patients used to take anti-hypertensive regularly, 24 respondents took irregularly. 36 diabetic respondents used to take anti hypertensive regularly but 7 were irregular. Out of 84 anti platelet receiver 60 were regular and 24 were irregular. 10 responder were taking anti coagulant regularly while 4 responder were irregular. 62 patient who were getting lipid lowering agent 40 of them were regular but 22 were irregular. Among the female responder 6 responder were taking regular OCP and 10 were taking irregularly.

The bar chart shows among the respondents those who had recurrent stroke most of them (60%, 60) had >10 score in Glasgow coma scale, among the respondents with haemorrhage majority of them (46%, 10) had score less than 5.

The table shows, among the respondents according to type of their stroke, infarction had greater proportion (78%) than hemorrhage (68%) in those who were aging more than 40 years in contrast with those under 40 years. To see the statistical significance of this difference we did a χ^2 test. The test shows that this difference is not significant statistically $\chi^2(df=1, n=100) = 0.779, p > 0.05$.

Figure 15: Distribution of the Respondents According to Their Glasgow Coma Scale in Different Types of Stroke (n=100)

Table 3: Relation between Age Group and Type of Stroke of the Respondents Had (n=100)

	Infarction	Hemorrhage	χ^2 value, df	P value
More than 40 years	61 (78%)	15 (68%)	0.7791, 1	0.463
Less than 40 years	17 (22%)	7 (32%)		
Total	78	22		

Figure 16: Distribution of the Respondents According to Territory Involved in Infarction (n=78)

The pie chart (Figure 16) shows among (out of 100 patients) the respondents 78 had infarction among them the CT scan report shows that majority of them Middle Cerebral Artery (MCA) (71%, 56), was the involved territory, Followed by Posterior Cerebral Artery (16%,12), Anterior Cerebral Artery (ACA) (8%, 6) and Basilar artery (5%, 4).

The pie chart (Figure 17) shows among the respondents those who had infarction regarding their regional involvement majority of them (41%, 23) had involvement in cerebral cortex, followed by Basal ganglia (21%, 12), Thalamus (29%, 16) and Internal capsule (9%,5).

The pie chart (Figure 18) shows the distribution of affected region of those 22 respondents, had hemorrhage. Among them in majority cases the affected region was the basal ganglia & internal capsule and thalamus (55%, 12), followed by temporoparietal region (36%, 8) and posterior fossa bleed (9%, 2).

Figure 17: Distribution of the Respondents Having Infarction in MCA Territory According to Their Regional Involvement (n=56)

Figure 18: Distribution of the Respondents (Having Hemorrhage) According to Their Region Affected (n=22)

Discussion

Stroke is a frequent cause of death and disability and is a major problem in most part of the world [37]. In the present study, the concern was to find out the facts related to recurrent stroke. It was found that majority of the respondents were male (72%), mean age 57.45 years and majority were from 60-69 age group (44). On the basis of socioeconomic status lower middle class contributed in greater proportion (46%). Majority of the respondents of this study had completed higher secondary completed educational background. Most of the event occurred during day time and a great number of responder were sedentary worker.

In present study, majority of the responder (78%) suffered from ischemic stroke and rest of them had haemorrhagic stroke [37]. [38], in a series of 154 patients with recurrent stroke found that, 30 (19.5%) were ICH, 16 (10.4%) were SAH and 102 (66.2%) were infarcts. Another study [39] found, infarction was commoner than haemorrhage. Out of 150 cases, 87 (58%) were infarcts and 63 (42%) were haemorrhage [54].

In this study among the respondents, 66 (66%) of them presented with hypertension, 42(42%) with diabetes mellitus, 46(46%) had dyslipidemia, and 35(35%) presented with heart disease. Again among the patient with heart disease, majority had IHD (63%,22), followed by arrhythmia (57%,20), valvular heart disease (54%,19) and congestive heart failure (CHF) (17%,6).

In present study majority (62%) were smoker, 22% chewed betelnuts, 12% betel leaf and 8% were alcoholic. [39] found risk factors were present in 141 cases and absent in 9. The commonest risk factor was smoking (40.66%) followed by hypertension (40%), obesity (34%), alcohol intake (30.6%) [54]. Tobacco chewing comprised 28.66% and diabetes mellitus in 6.6%. Heart disease was noted in 6% cases. [43] in 1999 retrospectively evaluated 200 patients of stroke. They reported common risk factors for recurrent stroke as tobacco use in 20%, hypercholesterolemia in 35%, hypertension in 13% and alcohol use in 10%. In the study by [44] in 2000, common risk factors in stroke were hypertension in 62%, diabetes mellitus in 38% and smoking in 28%.

In present study, in majority case middle cerebral artery (MCA) (71%) was the involved territory, followed by posterior cerebral artery (PCA) (16%), anterior cerebral artery (8%) and basilar artery (5%). [39] found that, the commonest vascular territory involved in recurrent stroke was the MCA territory (77%) followed by the PCA (11.49%) and the ACA (6.8%). The basilar artery territory was involved in 4.5% of cases. In a study by [45] 75% cases MCA infarction, 13% ACA and 8% PCA [54]. Both of the studies are comparable to our study in which we found, in majority cases Middle Cerebral Artery (MCA) (71%), was the involved territory,

Followed by Posterior Cerebral Artery (16%), Anterior Cerebral Artery (ACA) (8%) and Basilar artery (5%).

Conclusion

In conclusion, among the reported recurrent stroke individuals the ratio between male and female is 2.5:1, with mean age 57.45, majority of them from lower middle class, being married and a sedentary worker. Majority reported with ischemic stroke, found at day time with a history of illness commonly hypertension, diabetes mellitus or heart disease. Most of them reported with a complain of unable to move or weakness in part of body or vertigo. The initial rating on Glasgow coma scale was found poor in case of reported hemorrhage cases. This may reflect differences between reports in the types of recurrent strokes studied according to pathological subtype [ischemic or hemorrhagic], but there may be statistical instability of the result when predicting about large scale population because of the small numbers of recurrent strokes included and in depth interview was not possible.

Limitations

The limitations of the studies were as follows:

- This study was conducted an observation study on limited number of patients in a single hospital. Therefore, the results might not be sufficient to change clinical practice or policy recommendations.
- It was not possible at all, to maintain a specific time frame for all the respondents regarding their timing of CT scan. So, some of them had early CT scan reports (within 6 hours), some had even after 72 hours. As a result diagnostic variation due to this difference of duration could not be taken into consideration.
- Follow-up information was not available for all patients in the study sample.

Conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest.

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Author Contributions

Study design and data analysis: Dr. Md. Mahmudul Alam

Data collection: Dr. Md. Mahmudul Alam

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